

Month	Family Serving	Lunar Year	Month date (Solar Event)	
Month 1	Seraiah	Year 1	1st day is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Jeremiah			
3	Ezra			
4	Amariah			
5	Malluch			
6	Hattush			
7	Shecaniah		3rd day is the Vernal Equinox	
8	Rehum			
9	Meremoth			
10	Iddo			
11	Ginnethoi			
12	Abijah			
1	Mijamin	Year 2	12th day is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Maadiah			
3	Bilgah			
4	Shemaiah			
5	Joiarib			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Sallu		14th is the Vernal Equinox	
8	Amok			
9	Hilkiah			
10	Jedaiah			
11	Seraiah			
12	Jeremiah			
1	Ezra	Year 3	23rd day is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Amariah			
3	Malluch			
4	Hattush			
5	Shecaniah			
6	Rehum			
7	Meremoth		25th day is the Vernal Equinox	
8	Iddo			
9	Ginnethoi			
10	Abijah			
11	Mijamin			
12	Maadiah			
1	Bilgah	Year 4		
2	Shemaiah		4th day is the Autumnal Equinox	
3	Joiarib			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Sallu			
6	Amok			
7	Hilkiah			
8	Jedaiah		7th day is the Vernal Equinox	

9	Seraiah			
10	Jeremiah			
11	Ezra			
12	Amariah			
1	Malluch	Year 5		
2	Hattush		16th day is the Autumnal Equinox	
3	Shecaniah			
4	Rehum			
5	Meremoth			
6	Iddo			
7	Ginnethoi			
8	Abijah		18th day is the Vernal Equinox	
9	Mijamin			
10	Maadiah			
11	Bilgah			
12	Shemaiah			
1	Joiarib	Year 6		
2	Jedaiah		27th day is the Autumnal Equinox	
3	Sallu			
4	Amok			
5	Hilkiah			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Seraiah			
8	Jeremiah		29th day is the Vernal Equinox	
9	Ezra			
10	Amariah			
11	Malluch			
12	Hattush			
1	Shecaniah	Year 7		
2	Rehum			
3	Meremoth		9th day is the Autumnal Equinox	
4	Iddo			
5	Ginnethoi			
6	Abijah			
7	Mijamin			
8	Maadiah			
9	Bilgah		11 th day is Vernal Equinox	
10	Shemaiah			
11	Joiarib			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Sallu	Year 8		
2	Amok			
3	Hilkiah		20th is the Autumnal Equinox	
4	Jedaiah			
5	Seraiah			
6	Jeremiah			

7	Ezra			
8	Amariah			
9	Malluch		23rd is the Vernal Equinox	
10	Hattush			
11	Shecaniah			
12	Rehum			
1	Meremoth	Year 9		
2	Iddo			
3	Ginnethoi			
4	Abijah		2nd is the Autumnal Equinox	
5	Mijamin			
6	Maadiah			
7	Bilgah			
8	Shemaiah			
9	Joiarib			
10	Jedaiah		4th is the Vernal Equinox	
11	Sallu			
12	Amok			
1	Hilkiah	Year 10		
2	Jedaiah			
3	Seraiah			
4	Jeremiah		13th is the Autumnal Equinox	
5	Ezra			
6	Amariah			
7	Malluch			
8	Hattush			
9	Shecaniah			
10	Rehum		15th is the Vernal Equinox	
11	Meremoth			
12	Iddo			
1	Ginnethoi	Year 11		
2	Abijah			
3	Mijamin			
4	Maadiah		24th is the Autumnal Equinox	
5	Bilgah			
6	Shemaiah			
7	Joiarib			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Sallu			
10	Amok		26th is the Vernal Equinox	
11	Hilkiah			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Seraiah	Year 12		
2	Jeremiah			
3	Ezra			
4	Amariah			

5	Malluch		6th is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Hattush			
7	Shecaniah			
8	Rehum			
9	Meremoth			
10	Iddo			
11	Ginnethoi		9th is the Vernal Equinox	
12	Abijah			
1	Mijamin	Year 13		
2	Maadiah			
3	Bilgah			
4	Shemaiah			
5	Joiarib		18th is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Jedaiah			
7	Sallu			
8	Amok			
9	Hilkiah			
10	Jedaiah			
11	Seraiah		20th is the Vernal Equinox	
12	Jeremiah			
1	Ezra	Year 14		
2	Amariah			
3	Malluch			
4	Hattush			
5	Shecaniah		29th is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Rehum			
7	Meremoth			
8	Iddo			
9	Ginnethoi			
10	Abijah			
11	Mijamin			
12	Maadiah		1st is the Vernal Equinox	
1	Bilgah	Year 15		
2	Shemaiah			
3	Joiarib			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Sallu			
6	Amok		10th is the Autumnal Equinox	
7	Hilkiah			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Seraiah			
10	Jeremiah			
11	Ezra			
12	Amariah		12th is the Vernal Equinox	
1	Malluch	Year 16		
2	Hattush			

3	Shecaniah			
4	Rehum			
5	Meremoth			
6	Iddo		21st is the Autumnal Equinox	
7	Ginnethoi			
8	Abijah			
9	Mijamin			
10	Maadiah			
11	Bilgah			
12	Shemaiah		24th is the Vernal Equinox	
1	Joiarib	Year 17		
2	Jedaiah			
3	Sallu			
4	Amok			
5	Hilkiah			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Seraiah		4th is the Autumnal Equinox	
8	Jeremiah			
9	Ezra			
10	Amariah			
11	Malluch			
12	Hattush			
1	Shecaniah	Year 18	6th is the Vernal Equinox	
2	Rehum			
3	Meremoth			
4	Iddo			
5	Ginnethoi			
6	Abijah			
7	Mijamin		15th is the Autumnal Equinox	
8	Maadiah			
9	Bilgah			
10	Shemaiah			
11	Joiarib			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Sallu	Year 19	17th is the Vernal Equinox	
2	Amok			
3	Hilkiah			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Seraiah			
6	Jeremiah			
7	Ezra		26th is the Autumnal Equinox	
8	Amariah			
9	Malluch			
10	Hattush			
11	Shecaniah			
12	Rehum			

1	Meremoth	Year 20	28th is the Vernal Equinox	
2	Iddo			
3	Ginnethoi			
4	Abijah			
5	Mijamin			
6	Maadiah			
7	Bilgah			
8	Shemaiah		7th is the Autumnal Equinox	
9	Joiarib			
10	Jedaiah			
11	Sallu			
12	Amok			
1	Hilkiah	Year 21		
2	Jedaiah		10th is the Vernal Equinox	
3	Seraiah			
4	Jeremiah			
5	Ezra			
6	Amariah			
7	Malluch			
8	Hattush		19th is the Autumnal Equinox	
9	Shecaniah			
10	Rehum			
11	Meremoth			
12	Iddo			
1	Ginnethoi	Year 22		
2	Abijah		21st is the Vernal Equinox	
3	Mijamin			
4	Maadiah			
5	Bilgah			
6	Shemaiah			
7	Joiarib			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Sallu		1st is the Autumnal Equinox	
10	Amok			
11	Hilkiah			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Seraiah	Year 23		
2	Jeremiah			
3	Ezra		3rd is the Vernal Equinox	
4	Amariah			
5	Malluch			
6	Hattush			
7	Shecaniah			
8	Rehum			
9	Meremoth		12th is the Autumnal Equinox	
10	Iddo			

11	Ginnethoi			
12	Abijah			
1	Mijamin	Year 24		
2	Maadiah			
3	Bilgah		14th is the Vernal Equinox	
4	Shemaiah			
5	Joiarib			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Sallu			
8	Amok			
9	Hilkiah		23rd is the Autumnal Equinox	
10	Jedaiah			
11	Seraiah			
12	Jeremiah			
1	Ezra	Year 25		
2	Amariah			
3	Malluch		26th is the Vernal Equinox	
4	Hattush			
5	Shecaniah			
6	Rehum			
7	Meremoth			
8	Iddo			
9	Ginnethoi			
10	Abijah		5th is the Autumnal Equinox	
11	Mijamin			
12	Maadiah			
1	Bilgah	Year 26		
2	Shemaiah			
3	Joiarib			
4	Jedaiah		7th is the Vernal Equinox	
5	Sallu			
6	Amok			
7	Hilkiah			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Seraiah			
10	Jeremiah		16th is the Autumnal Equinox	
11	Ezra			
12	Amariah			
1	Malluch	Year 27		
2	Hattush			
3	Shecaniah			
4	Rehum		18th is the Vernal Equinox	
5	Meremoth			
6	Iddo			
7	Ginnethoi			
8	Abijah			

9	Mijamin			
10	Maadiah		27th is the Autumnal Equinox	
11	Bilgah			
12	Shemaiah			
1	Joiarib	Year 28		
2	Jedaiah			
3	Sallu			
4	Amok		29th is the Vernal Equinox	
5	Hilkiah			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Seraiah			
8	Jeremiah			
9	Ezra			
10	Amariah			
11	Malluch		9th is the Autumnal Equinox	
12	Hattush			
1	Shecaniah	Year 29		
2	Rehum			
3	Meremoth			
4	Iddo			
5	Ginnethoi		12th is the Vernal Equinox	
6	Abijah			
7	Mijamin			
8	Maadiah			
9	Bilgah			
10	Shemaiah			
11	Joiarib		21st is the Autumnal Equinox	
12	Jedaiah			
1	Sallu	Year 30		
2	Amok			
3	Hilkiah			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Seraiah		23rd is the Vernal Equinox	
6	Jeremiah			
7	Ezra			
8	Amariah			
9	Malluch			
10	Hattush			
11	Shecaniah			
12	Rehum		2nd is the Autumnal Equinox	
1	Meremoth	Year 31		
2	Iddo			
3	Ginnethoi			
4	Abijah			
5	Mijamin			
6	Maadiah		4th is the Vernal Equinox	

7	Bilgah			
8	Shemaiah			
9	Joiarib			
10	Jedaiah			
11	Sallu			
12	Amok		13th is the Autumnal Equinox	
1	Hilkiah	Year 32		
2	Jedaiah			
3	Seraiah			
4	Jeremiah			
5	Ezra			
6	Amariah		15th is the Vernal Equinox	
7	Malluch			
8	Hattush			
9	Shecaniah			
10	Rehum			
11	Meremoth			
12	Iddo		24th is the Autumnal Equinox	
1	Ginnethoi	Year 33		
2	Abijah			
3	Mijamin			
4	Maadiah			
5	Bilgah			
6	Shemaiah		27th is the Vernal Equinox	
7	Joiarib			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Sallu			
10	Amok			
11	Hilkiah			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Seraiah	Year 34	7th is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Jeremiah			
3	Ezra			
4	Amariah			
5	Malluch			
6	Hattush			
7	Shecaniah		9th is the Vernal Equinox	
8	Rehum			
9	Meremoth			
10	Iddo			
11	Ginnethoi			
12	Abijah			
1	Mijamin	Year 35	18th is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Maadiah			
3	Bilgah			
4	Shemaiah			

5	Joiarib			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Sallu		20th is the Vernal Equinox	
8	Amok			
9	Hilkiah			
10	Jedaiah			
11	Seraiah			
12	Jeremiah			
1	Ezra	Year 36	29th is the Autumnal Equinox	
2	Amariah			
3	Malluch			
4	Hattush			
5	Shecaniah			
6	Rehum			
7	Meremoth			
8	Iddo		1st is the Vernal Equinox	
9	Ginnethoi			
10	Abijah			
11	Mijamin			
12	Maadiah			
1	Bilgah	Year 37		
2	Shemaiah		10th is the Autumnal Equinox	
3	Joiarib			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Sallu			
6	Amok			
7	Hilkiah			
8	Jedaiah		13th is the Vernal Equinox	
9	Seraiah			
10	Jeremiah			
11	Ezra			
12	Amariah			
1	Malluch	Year 38		
2	Hattush		22nd is the Autumnal Equinox	
3	Shecaniah			
4	Rehum			
5	Meremoth			
6	Iddo			
7	Ginnethoi			
8	Abijah		24th is the Vernal Equinox	
9	Mijamin			
10	Maadiah			
11	Bilgah			
12	Shemaiah			
1	Joiarib	Year 39		
2	Jedaiah			

3	Sallu		4th is the Autumnal Equinox	
4	Amok			
5	Hilkiah			
6	Jedaiah			
7	Seraiah			
8	Jeremiah			
9	Ezra		6th is the Vernal Equinox	
10	Amariah			
11	Malluch			
12	Hattush			
1	Shecaniah	Year 40		
2	Rehum			
3	Meremoth		15th is the Autumnal Equinox	
4	Iddo			
5	Ginnethoi			
6	Abijah			
7	Mijamin			
8	Maadiah			
9	Bilgah		17th is the Vernal Equinox	
10	Shemaiah			
11	Joiarib			
12	Jedaiah			
1	Sallu	Year 41		
2	Amok			
3	Hilkiah		26th is the Autumnal Equinox	
4	Jedaiah			
5	Seraiah			
6	Jeremiah			
7	Ezra			
8	Amariah			
9	Malluch		29th is the Vernal Equinox	
10	Hattush			
11	Shecaniah			
12	Rehum			
1	Meremoth	Year 42		
2	Iddo			
3	Ginnethoi			
4	Abijah		8th is the Autumnal Equinox	
5	Mijamin			
6	Maadiah			
7	Bilgah			
8	Shemaiah			
9	Joiarib			
10	Jedaiah		10th is the Vernal Equinox	
11	Sallu			
12	Amok			

1	Hilkiah	Year 43		
2	Jedaiah			
3	Seraiah			
4	Jeremiah		19th is the Autumnal Equinox	
5	Ezra			
6	Amariah			
7	Malluch			
8	Hattush			
9	Shecaniah			
10	Rehum		21st is the Vernal Equinox	
11	Meremoth			
12	Iddo			
1	Ginnethoi	Year 44		
2	Abijah			
3	Mijamin			
4	Maadiah			
5	Bilgah		1st is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Shemaiah			
7	Joiarib			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Sallu			
10	Amok			
11	Hilkiah		3rd is the Vernal Equinox	
12	Jedaiah			
1	Seraiah	Year 45		
2	Jeremiah			
3	Ezra			
4	Amariah			
5	Malluch		12th is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Hattush			
7	Shecaniah			
8	Rehum			
9	Meremoth			
10	Iddo			
11	Ginnethoi		15th is the Vernal Equinox	
12	Abijah			
1	Mijamin	Year 46		
2	Maadiah			
3	Bilgah			
4	Shemaiah			
5	Joiarib		24th is the Autumnal Equinox	
6	Jedaiah			
7	Sallu			
8	Amok			
9	Hilkiah			
10	Jedaiah			

11	Seraiah		28th is the Vernal Equinox	
12	Jeremiah			
1	Ezra	Year 47		
2	Amariah			
3	Malluch			
4	Hattush			
5	Shecaniah			
6	Rehum		5th is the Autumnal Equinox	
7	Meremoth			
8	Iddo			
9	Ginnethoi			
10	Abijah			
11	Mijamin			
12	Maadiah		7th is the Vernal Equinox	
1	Bilgah	Year 48		
2	Shemaiah			
3	Joiarib			
4	Jedaiah			
5	Sallu			
6	Amok		16th is the Autumnal Equinox	
7	Hilkiah			
8	Jedaiah			
9	Seraiah			
10	Jeremiah			
11	Ezra			
12	Amariah		18th is the Vernal Equinox	
1	Malluch	Year 49		
2	Hattush			
3	Shecaniah			
4	Rehum			
5	Meremoth			
6	Iddo		27th is the Autumnal Equinox	
7	Ginnethoi			
8	Abijah			
9	Mijamin			
10	Maadiah			
11	Bilgah			
12	Shemaiah			
1	Joiarib	Year 50	1st Day is Vernal Equinox	
2	Jedaiah			
3	Sallu			
4	Amok			
5	Hilkiah			
6	Jedaiah			
ing for the Autumnal Equinox		10/7/50 morning is the Autumnal Equinox		